

Rice varieties for delayed planting

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Late onset of the monsoon, late receipt of water by tail end canal farmers, scarcity of labor during transplanting in areas where the rice crop is in succession with other crops, and other socioeconomic problems can lead to delayed transplanting, resulting in yield reduction.

To identify rice varieties suitable for different agroclimatic regions of India and with mechanisms for adaptability to late planting, we conducted trials with promising cultures, standard checks, and local checks during 1984, 1985, and 1986.

N as urea was applied at 60 kg/ha in 2 split doses — 75% incorporated at the last puddling, 25% 15-20 d later. P, potash, and Zn were applied as recommended. Seedlings were

Varieties evaluated for delayed planting at different locations. India, 1984-86.

Location	Planting date	Standard check		Local check		Test variety	
		Name	Yield (t/ha)	Name	Yield (t/ha)	Name	Yield (t/ha)
Maruteru, Andhra Pradesh	20 Aug 1984	IET7192	2.2	MTU7633	3.8	CR1018	4.1
Mandya, Karnataka	8 Sep 1986	IET7251	3.9	CTMI	3.7	Mandya Vijaya	5.4
Pattambi, Kerala	20 Jul 1985	IET7251	1.6	H4	2.7	CNM539	2.6
Titabar, Assam	10 Sep 1985	IET7251	3.1	Manoharsali	4.4	CNM539	4.2
Chinsurah, West Bengal	3 Sep 1985	IET7251	3.2	CNM539	3.5	NC492	4.0
Malda, West Bengal	30 Aug 1985	IET7251	1.6	CNM539	3.3	NC492	4.3
Mohanpur, West Bengal	30 Aug 1986	IET7251	3.7	CNM539	2.6	IR42	4.4
Kharagpur, West Bengal	2 Sep 1986	IET7251	4.8	CNM539	2.7	CR1016	5.5
Patna, Biha	15 Aug 1985	IET7251	4.3	Pankaj	2.5	CNM539	4.4

transplanted at 60 d, 20- × 15-cm spacing, from late Jul to early Sep. All test varieties except CNM539 at

Pattambi could be planted late without any significant reduction in yield (see table). □

Agronomic and yield characteristics of three elite upland rices in Tamil Nadu

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We evaluated 186 upland rice entries comprising local, indigenous, and exotic collections in upland experimental fields

at ARS from 1984 to 1987. Major entries were derived from hybrid combinations of two genotypes from different ecogeographic zones. They were compared with the local check Nootripathu and the improved check PMK 1. Three superior varieties — PM1390, AD35850, and IET7564 — performed better than the improved check PMK1 (see table).

The varieties are short statured (55 to 73 cm) and have medium, dense panicles

(16.4 to 19.5 cm) and 7 to 8 productive tillers. They mature in 90 to 110 d. Average maximum yields range from 2.6 to 3.1 t/ha.

The screened cultures are highly resistant to drought as well as to lodging and are suitable for the eastern arid zone of Tamil Nadu. □

Characteristics of elite upland rice hybrid derivatives and local checks. Tamil Nadu, India, 1984-87.

Variety	Parentage	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Productive tillers (no.)	Duration (d)	Av yield (t/ha)
PM1390	IR13564/ASD4	73	19.5	75	8	110	3.1
AD35850	ADT36/ADT29	59	18.6	69	8	108	3.0
IET7564	IRAT8/N22	55	16.4	59	7	90	2.6
PMK1 (improved check)	Co 25/ADT31	90	19.0	66	8	115	2.6
Nootripathu (local check)	Local land race	74	18.2	64	5	110	2.0

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